

Synthesis and Pharmacology of N-(N⁴-Aryl-N¹-Piperazinyl-alkyl) Phthalimides : CNS Depressants

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Manuscript received 21 May 1979, accepted 6 October 1979

Twenty one N-(N⁴-Aryl-N¹-Piperazinylmethyl/ethyl/propyl) Phthalimides were prepared in view of their expected CNS action. The piperazinylmethyl phthalimides were prepared through N-Mannich reaction of phthalimides with piperazines in presence of HCHO. These compounds were found to be inactive. The higher homologs, piperazinyl ethyl and propyl phthalimides, were synthesized by the reaction of N-(ω-bromo alkyl)-phthalimides with aryl piperazines. These derivatives exhibited tranquilizing effect on test animals and were non-toxic.

PIPERAZINE substituted compounds have a plethora of activities and have led to many interesting drugs.

N-Phenylpiperazine possesses CNS and cardiovascular activities and substitution on the second N-atom significantly modifies them¹. Thalidomide (I) which contains a phthalimide moiety, is a good hypnotic with devoid of toxicity². Many N-(N-dialkylamino-alkyl)-phthalimides (II) are reported to exhibit various pharmacological activities³⁻⁹. In these derivatives phthalimide functions acts as lipophilic moiety.

I

II

These observations prompted us to synthesize N-(N⁴-aryl-N¹-piperazinylalkyl)-phthalimides (Va-g, IXa-g and X-a-g) as possible CNS agents (Chart 1).

N-Aryl piperazines required for the present investigation were prepared following the method of C. B. Pollard.^{10,11} N-Mannich reaction of N-aryl piperazines (IV) with phthalimide (III) in presence of formaldehyde furnished N-(N⁴-aryl-N¹-piperazinylmethyl) phthalimides (V a-g). (Table 1). N-(2-Bromoethyl)-phthalimide (VIIIa) was prepared in good yield by modified Gabriel's method^{12,13}, employing K-phthalimide (VI) and 1,2-dibromoethane (VII a) in DMF. N-(3-Bromopropyl) phthalimide (VIII b) was prepared according to the literature method¹⁴ in which VI and VIIb were heated to high temperature. VIIIa and VIIIb were condensed with N-aryl piperazines in dry benzene at reflux in presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ to yield IX and X respectively (Table 1 and 2). Xa-g were isolated as hydrochlorides.

CHART-1

V a-g

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on Gallenkamp melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were run on Beckmann AccuLab 10 model and the values are in cm⁻¹ (wave numbers). NMR spectra were recorded on Varian-60 instrument at 60MHz frequency and the chemical shift values are in δ (ppm) with TMS as internal reference.

N-(N⁴-Phenyl-N¹-piperazinylmethyl) phthalimide (Va) III (1.47 g, 0.01 m) was dissolved in ab. alcohol (50 ml.). 1 ml. formalin (aq. 36%) and phenyl piper-

zine (1.61 g. 0.01 m) were added. The mixture refluxed for 1 hr and cooled. The precipitated solid was filtered and crystallized from ab. alcohol. m.p. 162-163°, yield 3.14 g (96.8%).

(Anal : Found : C, 71.9 ; H, 6.09 ; N, 13.16%.

Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₉N₃O₂ : C, 71.01 ; H, 5.96 ; N, 13.08%)

i.r. (KBr) 1698 and 1764 ($\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \quad | \quad \text{O} \\ || \quad | \quad || \\ -\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{C}- \end{array}$)
 n.m.r. (CDCl₃) : 2.84 and 3.14 (4H, t, -N¹< $\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2 \\ | \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{array}$ and
 4H, t, -N⁴< $\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2 \\ | \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{array}$ of piperazine ring resp.).
 4.7 (1H, s, >N-CH₂-N<¹), 6.7-7.34 (5H, m, N⁴-Ar), 7.5-7.9 (4H, m, phthalimide-Ar).

Compds. Vb-g were prepared similarly (Table-1)

pressure. The concentrated solution was poured in water and extracted with CHCl₃. The CHCl₃ layer was concentrated and the residue crystallised from dil. alcohol (50%)

m.p. 81-82° yield 20.6 g. (81%)

i.r. (KBr) : 1700 and 1760 ($\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \quad | \quad \text{O} \\ || \quad | \quad || \\ -\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{C}- \end{array}$)
 710 (C-Br)

N-(N⁴-Phenyl-N¹-piperazinyloethyl)-phthalimide (IXa)

VIIIa (2.54 g, 0.01 m), phenyl piperazine (1.61 g, 0.01 m) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (3g) were refluxed in dry benzene for 20 hr under dry atm. The mixture was filtered and concentrated. The residue was crystallised from alcohol.

m.p. 159-160° yield 2.00 g. (59.6%).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF N-(N⁴-ARYL-N¹-PIPERAZINYLLALKYL) PHTHALIMIDES

No.	n	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Elemental Analysis %					
					C		H		N	
					Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found
Va	1	H	162-163	96.77	71.01	71.90	5.96	6.09	13.08	13.16
Vb	1	2-CH ₃	145-146	84.97	71.62	71.50	6.31	6.22	12.53	12.37
Vc	1	3-CH ₃	131-132	76.03	71.62	71.69	6.31	6.25	12.53	12.42
Vd	1	4-CH ₃	150-151	89.44	71.62	71.77	6.31	6.42	12.53	12.51
Ve	1	2-Cl	132-133	56.21	64.13	64.13	5.10	5.03	11.81	11.77
Vf	1	3-Cl	161-162	98.36	64.13	64.28	5.10	5.21	11.81	11.67
Vg	1	4-Cl	169-170	88.24	64.13	64.30	5.10	5.00	11.81	11.73
IXa	2	H	159-160	59.63	71.62	71.71	6.31	6.25	12.53	12.80
IXb	2	2-CH ₃	140-141	72.97	72.18	72.03	6.64	6.50	12.03	12.15
IXc	2	3-CH ₃	136-137	52.94	72.18	72.09	6.64	6.53	12.03	12.17
IXd	2	4-CH ₃	158-159	60.10	72.18	72.29	6.64	6.47	12.03	11.91
IXe	2	2-Cl	111-112	37.85	64.95	64.77	5.45	5.57	11.36	11.52
IXf	2	3-Cl	166-167	56.78	64.95	64.82	5.45	5.61	11.36	11.20
IXg	2	4-Cl	165-166	54.07	64.95	65.03	5.45	5.31	11.36	11.42

N-(2-Bromoethyl) phthalimide (VIII a)

VIIa (37.6 g, 0.2m) and DMF (100 ml) were stirred and VI (18.5 g., 0.1 m) added in portions. When the addition was complete the mix. was heated to 10J° on water bath and stirred for 6-8 hours. DMF and ex. VIIa were removed by distillation under reduced

Anal : Found : C, 71.71 ; H, 6.25 ; N, 12.80%

Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₁N₃O₂ : C, 71.62 ; H, 6.31 ; N, 12.53%)

i.r. (KBr) : 1710, and 1761 ($\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \quad | \quad \text{O} \\ || \quad | \quad || \\ -\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{C}- \end{array}$)

n.m.r. (CDCl₃) : 2.7 and 3.13 (4H, t, -N¹<CH₂
and 4H, t, -N⁴<CH₂ of piperazine ring resp.),

2.7 (2H, t, β-CH₂), 3.88 (2H, t, α-CH₂),

6.7-7.4 (5H, m, N⁴-Ar), 7.6-7.9 (4H, m, phthalimide Ar)

Compds. IX b-g were prepared similarly (Table 1).

N-(N⁴-Phenyl-N¹-piperazinypropyl) phthalimide (Xa)

VIII b¹⁴ (2.68 g, 0.01 m), phenylpiperazine (1.61 g, 0.01 m) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (3g) were refluxed in dry C₆H₆ under dry atm. for 20 hours. The reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate concentrated. The residue was taken in ab. alcohol and dry HCl gas was passed through it till the solution was acidic. The ppt. of hydrochloride was filtered and crystallized from ab. alcohol, m.p. 200-202°, yield : 1.87 (44.5%).

Pharmacology :

Gross behavioural effect and acute toxicity of the compounds suspended in twin-80 solution was studied in albino mice of Haffkin Strain by intraperitoneal administration using 10 animals per dose (doses selected were 900, 600, 300 and 100 mg/kg). Reduced spontaneous motor activity (as recorded on actophotometer), ataxia, loss of reflexes, reduced alertness and abnormal gait implied depression of CNS. The N-Mannich bases Va-g showed no effect on CNS even at the highest dose of 900 mg/kg. IXa-g and Xa-g produced mild to severe sedation in test animals. All the compounds have LD₅₀ > 900 mg/kg, except Xe which has LD₅₀ : 750 mg/kg. This showed that the compounds are devoid of toxicity. At higher doses they induced sedation while at lower doses they exhibited tranquillizing effect. Xe showed significant effect and found to be the most active. Gross behavioural observation classified the compounds as tranquilizers. Further screening in this direction is in progress.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF N-(N⁴-ARYL-N¹-PIPERAZINYLPYR) PHTHALIMIDES. 2HCl

No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Elemental Analysis %			
				Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found
Xa	H	200-202	44.49	10.00	9.91	16.87	16.80
Xb	2-CH ₃	223-225	29.93	9.67	9.52	16.33	16.43
Xc	3-CH ₃	217-219	48.35	9.67	9.62	16.33	16.30
Xd	4-CH ₃	205-206	49.53	9.67	9.59	16.33	16.22
Xe	2-Cl	212-213	42.22	9.24	9.33	23.39	23.31
Xf	3-Cl	216-218	43.96	9.24	9.20	23.39	23.49
Xg	4-Cl	227-228	49.03	9.24	9.18	23.39	23.33

The base of Xa was prepared (for analysis) by dissolving the hydrochloride in H₂O and basifying it with 10% NaOH. The base was crystallised with dil. Alcohol. m. p. 125-126° (Anal: Found C, 72.3; H, 6.55; N, 12.18%. Calcd for C₂₁H₂₃N₃O₂: C, 72.18; H, 6.63; N, 12.03% i.r. (KBr): 1708 and 1761

(-C-N-C-), n. m. r. (CDCl₃) : 1.9 (2H, m, β-CH₂), 2.44 (4H, t, -N¹<CH₂ of piperazine), 2.5.

(2H, t, γ-CH₂), 3.4 (4H, t, -N⁴<CH₂ of piperazine), 3.76 (2H, t, α-CH₂), 6.7-7.3 (5H, m, N⁴-Ar), 7.5-7.86 (4H, m, phthalimide Ar). Compounds. X b-g were prepared similarly (Table 2).

Acknowledgement

Acknowledgement is due to Shri S. M. Gupte, Chemistry Dept., for the pharmacological evaluation of the compounds. One of the authors (SDS) is grateful to U.G.C. for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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